

Template synthesis of novel 16-membered tetraazamacrocyclic transition metal complexes : DNA cleavage and antimicrobial studies

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Abstract : A new series of 16-membered tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of type $[ML]X_2$ [where $M = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, VO^{IV}, Cd^{II}$ and Mn^{II} ; $X_2 = 2Cl^-, SO_4^{2-}$] by incorporating an N_4 donor site has been synthesized via the template condensation of *m*-phenylenediamine, formaldehyde, *p*-anisidine and metal salts in 1 : 2 : 1 : 0.5 molar ratio. The structural features of the complexes have been confirmed by microanalytical data, IR, UV-Vis, 1H NMR, ESR and CV techniques. The UV-Vis, magnetic susceptibility and ESR spectral data of the complexes suggest a square-planar geometry around the central metal ion except VO^{IV} complex which has square-pyramidal geometry. The electrochemical behaviour, the anodic and cathodic potential and the number of electrons transferred were calculated using cyclic voltammogram. The X-band EPR spectrum of copper complex in DMSO at 300 K and 77 K were recorded and its salient features are reported. The antimicrobial data show good results. The nuclease activity of the above metal complexes shows that only copper complex cleaves CT-DNA through redox chemistry in the presence of oxidant.

Keywords : Tetraazamacrocyclic complexes, CT-DNA, nuclease activity.

Introduction

A significant rising interest in the design of metal compounds as drugs and diagnostic agents is currently observed in the area of scientific inquiry appropriately termed medicinal chemistry¹. Investigations in this area focus mostly on the speciation of metal species in biological media, based on possible interactions of these metal ions with diverse biomolecules, in an effort to contribute to future development of new therapeutics or diagnostic agents²⁻⁴.

Tetraaza molecules, especially when coordinated to metal centers, are considerable to be model metalloporphyrins and metalocorrins due to the presence of four nitrogen donor sites in a ringed structure^{5,6}. Macrocycles have been studied extensively and are best prepared with the aid of metal ions as templates to direct the condensation reaction towards ring closure⁷. However, there are relatively few reports on macrocyclic complexes containing all nitrogen heteroatoms in a fully saturated macrocyclic frame work⁸. Among polyazamacrocycles, tetraaza species have been most effectively studied. A large number of macrocyclic complexes have been prepared^{9,10} by the template condensation of primary diamine, formaldehyde and ammonia. It has been reported that many macrocyclic complexes in which the

tetraazamoiety is part of the macrocyclic frame work¹¹. Earlier, Jie and coworkers¹² successfully synthesized macrocyclic copper(II) complexes with formaldehyde and primary amine using the template synthetic technique and also studied the interaction of macrocyclic copper(II) complexes with calf thymus DNA. A literature search reveals that a large number of tetraazamacrocyclic transition metal complexes have been prepared and characterized but no work has been done on the template condensation of formaldehyde, *m*-phenylenediamine, *p*-anisidine and metal salts in ethanol medium and their DNA cleavage study using calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) by gel electrophoresis technique to understand the selectivity and efficiency of DNA recognized and cleaved by macrocyclic metal complexes, and to develop new effective cleaving agents or useful DNA probes.

Results and discussion

The complexes were found to be air stable and insoluble in water, but soluble in DMSO and DMF. The analytical data of the complexes together with some physical properties are summarized in Table 1. The thermal analytical data showed that there are no water molecules in the complexes. The microanalytical and mass data of the complexes correspond well with the general formula

Table 1. Physical characterization, analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of the complexes

Compd.	Molecular formula	Colour	Yield (%)	Found (Calcd.) (%)				$(\Lambda_m) \times 10^{-3}$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
				M	C	H	N		
[CuL]Cl ₂	CuC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Black	58	9.6 (9.9)	55.4 (55.9)	5.0 (5.2)	12.5 (13.0)	100.2	1.75
[NiL]Cl ₂	NiC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Brown	62	9.0 (9.2)	56.1 (56.3)	5.0 (5.3)	12.8 (13.1)	120.9	-
[CoL]Cl ₂	CoC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Brown	54	8.9 (9.2)	56.1 (56.3)	5.2 (5.3)	12.8 (13.1)	127.0	3.56
[MnL]Cl ₂	MnC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Brown	63	8.3 (8.6)	56.4 (56.6)	5.0 (5.3)	12.8 (13.2)	104.5	5.52
[ZnL]Cl ₂	ZnC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Light yellow	61	9.9 (10.2)	55.4 (55.7)	4.9 (5.3)	12.7 (13.0)	111.7	-
[VOL]SO ₄	VC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₇ S	Green	64	7.4 (7.6)	53.1 (53.5)	4.9 (5.1)	12.1 (12.5)	140.5	1.68
[CdL]Cl ₂	CdC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Yellow	58	15.8 (16.2)	51.4 (51.9)	4.6 (4.9)	11.7 (12.1)	132.4	-
[HgL]Cl ₂	HgC ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	Yellow	61	25.1 (25.6)	45.7 (46.1)	4.1 (4.3)	10.4 (10.7)	124.8	-

[ML]X₂ [where M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, VO^{IV}, Cd^{II} and Mn^{II}; X₂ = 2Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻; L = C₃₀H₃₄N₆O₂]. The complexes show higher conductance values in DMF solution (100.2–140.5 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) which support their electrolytic nature and are consistent with other related metal complexes¹³.

The ESI mass spectrum of the copper complex shows a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 644 which confirms the stoichiometry of metal chelates as [ML]X₂ type. It is also supported by the "Nitrogen Rule", since the complex possesses six nitrogen atoms. Further, the mass spectra of the other complexes support the above stoichiometry.

Infrared spectra : The preliminary identification of the macrocyclic complexes was done from their IR spectra. The complexes give no bands assignable to carbonyl group stretching modes. The sharp band observed around 3210 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})$ of the coordinated secondary amines. A medium intensity band appearing in the 2830–2960 cm^{-1} region corresponds to $\nu(\text{CH})$. The complexes show bands at 1405–1440, 1050–1080 and 715–730 cm^{-1} regions which can be assigned to phenyl ring vibrations¹⁴. In all of the metal complexes, a new band seen in the 450–500 cm^{-1} region is probably due to the formation of M–N bonds. In addition to the other bands, the vanadyl complex shows an additional band at 960 cm^{-1} attributed to the V=O frequency¹⁵.

Electronic spectra : The electronic absorption spectra of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and VO^{IV} complexes were recorded at

300 K. The absorption region assigned and the proposed geometry of the complexes are given in Table 2. From the data of this table, a square-planar geometry has been assigned for the complexes except VO^{IV} complex, which has square-pyramidal geometry. These values are comparable with that of the other reported complexes^{16–19}.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra : The ¹H NMR spectrum of the zinc complex exhibited broad signal at

Table 2. Electronic absorption spectral data of the compounds

Compd.	Solvent	Absorption (cm^{-1})	Band assignment	Geometry
CuL	DMF	37310	INCT	Square planar
		28409	INCT	
		17241	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	
NiL	DMF	38314	INCT	Square planar
		28280	INCT	
		21597	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$	
		18905	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$	
CoL	DMF	38610	INCT	Square planar
		27950	INCT	
		9685	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$	
VOL	DMF	33510	INCT	Square pyramidal
		26720	INCT	
		18595	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$	
		12531	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$	

δ 6.3 ppm which can be assigned to the secondary amino (C-NH-C, 4H) group. The other signals observed at δ 3.5 ppm and δ 2.7 ppm may be due to the $-\text{OCH}_3$ protons of *p*-anisidine and aldehyde moieties (N-CH₂-N, 8H) respectively. The complex also shows a multiplet in the region δ 7.0–7.6 ppm which is assigned to aromatic protons.

Electron spin resonance spectra : The EPR spectrum of copper complex, recorded in DMSO at 300 (RT) and 77 K (LNT) provides useful information which are important in studying the metal ion environment. The RT spectrum shows one intense absorption band in the high field region and it is isotropic, due to the tumbling motion of the molecules. But LNT spectrum shows four well resolved peaks with low field region and one intense peak in the high field region. The magnetic moment of the copper complex is 1.75 B.M. which corresponds to one unpaired electron, indicating that the complex is mononuclear. This fact was also evident from the absence of half field signal at 1600 G due to the $m_s = \pm 2$ transitions, ruling out any Cu-Cu interaction²⁰. The complex exhibits the g_{\parallel} value of 2.29 and g_{\perp} value of 2.07. The g -tensor values of the copper complex can be used to derive the ground state. In square-planar complexes, the unpaired electron lies in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital giving $^2B_{1g}$ as the ground state with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$, while the unpaired electron lies in the d_{z^2} orbital giving $^2A_{1g}$ as the ground state with $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel} > 2$. From the observed values, it is clear that $A_{\parallel} = 150 > A_{\perp} = 40$; $g_{\parallel} = 2.29$; $g_{\perp} = 2.07 > 2$ and coincide well with related systems which suggest that the complex has square-planar geometry and system is axially symmetric²¹⁻²³. This is also supported by the fact that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. In the axial spectra, the g -values are related with exchange interaction coupling constant (G) by the expression,

$$G = \frac{g_{\parallel} - 2.0023}{g_{\perp} - 2.0023}$$

According to Hathaway²⁴, if the G value is larger than four, the exchange interaction is negligible because the local tetragonal axes are aligned parallel or slightly misaligned. If the value of G is less than four, the exchange interaction is considerable and the local tetragonal axes are misaligned. For the present copper complex, the G value is 4.2 which suggest that the local tetragonal axes are aligned parallel or slightly misaligned and consistent with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state.

The ESR spectrum of the vanadyl complex, recorded

in DMSO solution at 300 and 77 K, shows a typical eight line and sixteen line pattern respectively. The isotropic ESR parameters $g_{\text{iso}} = 1.92$ and $A_{\text{iso}} = 101$ can be calculated from the position spacing of the resonance lines from the room temperature solution spectrum of the complex. The spectrum is like a typical eight line pattern which shows that a single vanadium is present in the molecule i.e. it is a monomer. In the frozen solid state, the spectrum shows two types of resonance components, one set due to the parallel features and the other set due to the perpendicular features, which indicate axially symmetric anisotropy with well resolved sixteen line hyperfine splitting, characteristic of an interaction between the electron and vanadium nuclear spin. From the anisotropic spectrum, the anisotropic parameters were calculated. The observed order ($A_{\parallel} = 173 > A_{\perp} = 72$; $g_{\perp} = 2.01 > g_{\parallel} = 1.95$) indicates that the unpaired electron is present in the d_{xy} orbital with square-pyramidal geometry around the VO^{IV} chelate^{25,26}.

Based on the above spectral and analytical data, the proposed structure of the metal complexes is given in Fig. 1.

Cyclic voltammetric study : The cyclic voltammogram of copper complex (0.1 M) in DMF solution recorded in the absence of molecular oxygen at room temperature in 0.7 to -1.7 V potential range at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1}

Fig. 1. The proposed structure of the complexes.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities of investigated compounds (minimum inhibitory concentration $\times 10^{-2} M$)

Compd.	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>R. bataicola</i>
CuL	3.1	3.7	4.5	3.9	4.5	4.2
NiL	3.9	4.2	4.4	4.5	5.1	5.3
CoL	4.1	4.7	4.4	4.6	4.9	5.4
MnL	4.5	4.6	4.3	4.7	5.2	4.8
ZnL	4.7	4.6	4.2	4.9	5.1	5.2
VOL	4.4	4.7	4.4	4.2	5.2	5.4
CdL	4.3	4.5	4.8	4.4	5.1	5.3
HgL	4.2	4.7	4.4	4.6	5.2	5.4

indicates that it is a quasi-reversible two electron process. A note worthy feature has been observed in the cyclic voltammogram of Cu^{II} complex during the forward scan. It shows cathodic reduction peaks, one at 0.29 V and another at -0.80 V which are attributed to reduction of $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{0}}$ respectively. During the reverse scan, it shows two anodic oxidation peaks, one at -0.67 V and another at 0.25 V which are attributed to oxidation of $\text{Cu}^{\text{0}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ respectively.

The cyclic voltammogram of oxovanadium complex (0.1 M), recorded in DMSO at 300 K in the potential range +1.2 to -1.3 V shows the peak at $E_{\text{pc}} = 0.06$ V in the cathodic side which is assigned to the reduction of $\text{VO}^{\text{IV}}/\text{VO}^{\text{III}}$. In the anodic side, the peak at $E_{\text{pa}} = 0.94$ V is assigned to the oxidation of $\text{VO}^{\text{IV}}/\text{VO}^{\text{V}}$.²⁷

Antimicrobial activity : For *in vitro* antimicrobial activity, the investigated compounds were tested against the bacteria *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizoctonia bataicola*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of the investigated compounds are summarized in Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of chelation theory. On chelation, the polarity of the metal ion will be reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with donor groups. Further, it increases the delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring and enhances the penetration of the complexes into lipid membranes and blocking of the metal binding sites in the enzymes of microorganisms. These complexes also disturb the respiration process of the cell and thus block the synthesis of proteins, which restricts further growth of the organisms²⁸.

Nuclease activity : The cleavage efficiency of the complexes compared to that of the control is due to their

efficient DNA-binding ability. The metal complexes are able to convert super coiled DNA (Form-I) into open circular DNA (Form-II). The general oxidative mechanisms proposed account of DNA cleavage by hydroxyl radicals via abstraction of a hydrogen atom from sugar units and predict the release of specific residues arising from transformed sugars, depending on the position from which the hydrogen atom is removed²⁹. The cleavage is inhibited by the free radical scavengers implying that hydroxyl radical or peroxy derivatives mediate the cleavage reaction. The reaction is modulated by metallo-complexes bound hydroxyl radical or a peroxy species generated from the co-reactant H_2O_2 .

In the present study, the CT-DNA gel electrophoresis experiment was conducted at 35 °C using our synthesized complexes in the presence of H_2O_2 as an oxidant. As can be seen from the results (Fig. 2), at very low concentration, few complexes exhibit nuclease activity in the presence of H_2O_2 . Control experiments using DNA alone do not show any significant cleavage of CT-DNA

Lanes left to right →
 Lane 1, DNA alone
 Lane 2, DNA + VO^{IV} complex
 Lane 3, DNA + Mn^{II} complex
 Lane 4, DNA + Cd^{II} complex
 Lane 5, DNA + Hg^{II} complex
 Lane 6, DNA + Zn^{II} complex
 Lane 7, DNA + Ni^{II} complex
 Lane 8, DNA + Co^{II} complex
 Lane 9, DNA + Cu^{II} complex

Fig. 2. Changes in the agarose gel electrophoretic pattern of calf-thymus DNA induced by H_2O_2 and $[\text{ML}]\text{X}_2$ complexes.

even on longer exposure time. From the observed results, we conclude that copper complex (lane 9) cleaves DNA completely as compared to control DNA while other complexes (lanes 2–8) cleave DNA in the presence of H_2O_2 . Further, the presence of a smear in the gel diagram indicates the presence of radical cleavage³⁰.

Experimental

Materials and methods : The chemicals such as formaldehyde, *m*-phenylenediamine, *p*-anisidine and various metal salts were of Merck products and used as supplied. For the voltammetric experiments, tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) used as supporting electrolyte, was purchased from Sigma. Anhydrous grade ethanol, DMF and DMSO were purified according to standard procedures. Microanalytical data of the compounds were recorded at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility, Central Drug Research Institute (SAIF, CDRI), Lucknow. The ESI mass spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), Indian Institute of Technology, Mumbai. The IR spectra of the samples were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer in 4000–400 cm^{-1} range using KBr pellet. The UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer using DMF as solvent. The X-band ESR spectra of the complex was recorded at 300 K and 77 K at IIT, Mumbai using TCNE (tetracyanoethylene) as the *g*-marker. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were carried out by Guoy balance using copper sulphate as the calibrant. Electrochemical studies were carried out using EG&G Princeton Applied Research Potentiostat/Galvanostat Model 273A, controlled by M270 software. CV measurements were performed using a glassy carbon working electrode, platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. All solutions were purged with N_2 for 30 min prior to each set of experiments. The molar conductance of the complexes was measured using a Systronic conductivity bridge in DMF solution. Solutions of CT-DNA (calf thymus DNA) in 50 mM NaCl/50 mM tris-HCl (pH = 7.2) gave a ratio of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm, A_{260}/A_{280} of ca. 1.8–1.9, indicating that the DNA was sufficiently free of protein contamination. The DNA concentration was determined by the UV absorbance at 260 nm after 1 : 100 dilutions. The molar absorption coefficient was taken as 6600 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Stock solutions were kept at 4 °C and used after not more than 4 days. Doubly distilled H_2O was used to prepare the buffer. The antimicrobial activities of the complexes were carried out by well-diffusion method.

Syntheses of complexes : To a stirred ethanol solution of metal salts (0.01 *M*) slowly added *m*-phenylenediamine (0.02 *M*), formaldehyde (0.04 *M*) and *p*-anisidine (0.02 *M*). The mixture was heated under reflux for ca. 24 h. The solution was filtered under hot condition and the filtrate was allowed to stand at room temperature. The precipitate formed was filtered off, washed with ethanol and further dried *in vacuo*.

Antimicrobial activity : The *in vitro* biological screening effects of the investigated compounds were tested against the bacteria : *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* by the well diffusion method, using agar nutrient as the medium. The antifungal activities of the compounds were evaluated by the well diffusion method against the fungi viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizoctonia bataicola* cultured on potato dextrose agar as medium. The stock solution (10^{-2} *M*) was prepared by dissolving the compounds in DMSO and the solutions were serially diluted in order to find the MIC values. In a typical procedure³¹, a well was made on the agar medium inoculated with microorganisms. The well was filled with the test solution using a micropipette and the plate was incubated for 24 h in the case of bacteria and 72 h for fungi at 35 °C. During this period, the test solution diffused and the growth of the inoculated microorganisms was affected. The inhibition zone was developed, at which the concentration was noted.

Gel electrophoresis : The gel electrophoresis experiments were performed by incubation at 35 °C for 2 h as follows : CT-DNA 30 μM , 50 μM each complex and 50 μM H_2O_2 in 50 μM tris-HCl buffer (pH = 7.2) were electrophoresed for 2 h at 50 V on 1% agarose gel using tris-acetic acid-EDTA buffer, pH = 8.3. After electrophoresis, the gel was stained using 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ EB and photographed under UV light.

Conclusion :

In this work, new transition metal complexes have been synthesized by template method and characterized on the basis of analytical and spectral data. All the complexes exhibit square-planar geometry around the central metal ion except VO^{IV} complex which has square-pyramidal geometry. The antimicrobial data show good results. All the complexes showed enhanced nuclease activity in the presence of oxidant.

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